

A Study to Evaluate the Effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme on Reproductive Health Care Among Adolescent Girls of Jaihind English Medium High School At Ankola Uttar Kannada District, Karnataka

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Abstract: Background: Reproductive health deals with the reproductive processes, functions and systems in the least stages of life. Reproductive health includes sexual health, the aim of which is that the enhancement of life and private relations. And not merely counselling and care associated with reproduction and sexually transmitted diseases. The aim of the study was to gauge the effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme (PTP) on reproductive health care among adolescent girls. **Aims and Objectives:** The study was conducted to assess the extent of data regarding reproductive health care among adolescent girls, to gauge the effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme (PTP) on reproductive health care among adolescent girls, and to seek out association between knowledge scores and selected demographic variables among adolescent girls. **Materials and Methods:** 40 students studying at 10th standard were selected by purposive sampling technique. They were assessed for the extent of data regarding reproductive health care by using structured knowledge questionnaire on the primary day pretest followed by Planned Teaching Programme for one hour. The posttest was conducted on seventh day by using same tool. **Results:** Statistically significant effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme was found. In pretest knowledge scores there was significant association was found with demographical variables like age and occupation of oldsters, where as in posttest knowledge scores there was significant association was found with education of oldsters and former knowledge. **Conclusion:** The general findings of the study revealed that there was a big increase in knowledge level of scholars after administration of planned teaching programme regarding reproductive health. The knowledge regarding reproductive health was before planned teaching and it increased up, after planned teaching.

Keywords: Planned Teaching Programme, adolescent girls, reproductive health care.

Introduction

Reproductive health should be verified through a life cycle approach because it affects both men and ladies from infancy to adulthood. Reproductive health at any age profoundly affects health later in life. Adolescence could also be a transitional stage of physical and physiological development that generally occurs during the quantity from puberty to legal adulthood. According to World Health organization (WHO) health is defined as a state complete physical, mental and social wellbeing and merely the absence of diseases or infirmity. Reproductive health addresses the reproductive process functions and system in the least stages of life [1].

According to the United Nations Population Fund Association (UNPFA), unmet needs for sexual and reproductive health deprive women of the right to make “crucial choice about their

own bodies and typically nurture children, so their reproductive health is inspirable from gender equality denial of such rights also worsens poverty [1].

Adolescence reproductive and sexual health has been identified as key strategies within the reproductive and child health programme under the national rural health mission. Adolescence could also be a period of increased risk taking and thus susceptibility to behavioural problems at the time of puberty and new concerns about the reproductive health. Majority of the adolescents still do not have access to information and education on sexuality, reproduction and sexual and reproductive health and rights, nor do they need access to preventive and therefore the curative services [2].

Family planning is that the practice of controlling the quantity of kids during a family and thus the intervals between their birth contemporary notions of contraception, however tend to place a women and her child bearing decisions at the centre of the discussion, then notions of women's empowerment and reproductive autonomy have gained traction in many parts of the earth. Regular prenatal visits can help doctor to observe the pregnancy and identify any problems or complications before they become serious prenatal care. Chance of a secure and a healthy delivery, while most attention to pregnancy care focuses on the months of pregnancy, postpartum care is vital too [3].

One of the absolute best causes of maternal death worldwide is that the abortion related complications, the principles for the management for the abortion complications should be adapted on the thought of local conditions, availability of drugs, instruments, training, national standards and regulations. Prevention and management of reproductive tract infection and sexually transmitted diseases are one of the key reproductive health issues for both males and females. Reproductive tract infection and Sexually transmitted diseases pose continuing and high health problems. To prevent sexually transmitted diseases, the foremost thing to avoid sexual contact with the one that has reproductive tract infection or the opposite communicable diseases. It is vital many to avoid wasting to save lots of the kids works to reinforce health and nutrition of mother's newborn babies and kids with special attention to poor and vulnerable communities.

There should provide valuable communities. There should provide valuable evidence to increase government funding and influence global and national policies, working with governments, schools and non-profit partners, it improve the standard, availability and use of proven health and nutrition programme [4].

A woman's reproductive system is delicate and complicated system within the body. It is important to need steps to protect it from infections and injuries and stop problems including some future health problems. The quality reproductive health care may be a crucial determinant to make up an honest, better society within the longer term. To reinforce the reproductive health the upper health services and education regarding the reproductive health must be provided [4].

Infertility is a crucial reproductive ill health that's now mostly seen in many individuals. It's the biological inability of a female to become pregnant during an year or more of unprotected intercourse. A number of the treatment for the infertility includes hormone treatment, fertility drugs and surgery. Additionally, assisted reproduction uses various medical techniques to fertilize an egg. Researchers undertook this study considering the subject of interest and since of the development of data among the scholars. By the researchers experience and understanding the importance of the subject the investigators felt the necessity to pick the subject for the research study [4].

Materials and Methods

The one group pretest posttest pre experimental design was used. This study was conducted on 40 10th standard students of Jaihind English Medium School Ankola, Uttara Kannada district, Karnataka. The character of study was explained to the themes and written consent was obtained. The themes were selected by purposive non probability sampling method supported inclusion criteria. The structured knowledge questionnaire was used for data collection. The tool consists of six inquiries to get socio demographic data, and 45 items to assess the extent of knowledge regarding reproductive health. The tool was validated by experts in field of Public health nursing. Pre-test was conducted by using structured knowledge questionnaire followed by administration of planned teaching programme on same day of pre-test. The post test was conducted on seventh day of pre-test. The collected data was organized and analyzed supported the objectives by using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results

Findings associated with socio demographic variables: majority of Samples 85% (34) belonged to age bracket of 13-15years, 75% (30) were Hindus, parents education 40% (16) was SSLC, parents occupation 60% (24) was Business, 52.5% (21) had previous knowledge about reproductive health care, 37.5% (15) had knowledge about reproductive health care through internet. Findings associated with pre-test and post-test knowledge scores: mean of pretest is 18.50, median 19.25, mode 19.13 and variance is 3 and posttest mean 33.2, median 33.25, mode 34.78 and variance is 2.11. This reveals significant gain in knowledge of mean, median, and range scores after administering Planned Teaching Programme (PTP). Effectiveness of Planned Teaching Programme (PTP) in terms of gain in posttest knowledge scores: calculated paired 't' value ($t_{\text{calculated}} = 69.63$) is bigger than tabulated value ($t_{\text{table}} = 7.81$). Hence H_1 is accepted. This means that the gain in knowledge score is statistically significant at p.

Discussion

Mean of pretest is 18.5, median 19.25, mode 19.13 and standard deviation is 3 and posttest mean 33.2, median 33.25, mode 34.78 and standard deviation is 2.11. This reveals significant gain in knowledge of mean, median, and range scores after administering Planned Teaching Programme (PTP). The statistical analysis demonstrates that an increase in knowledge level of students, regarding reproductive health care was significant with 't' calculated value of 69.63 which is greater than 't' tabulated value 7.81. So the planned teaching programme was effective in improving the knowledge level among the students regarding reproductive health care. In pretest knowledge scores there was significant association was found with demographical variables such as age and occupation of parents, where as in posttest knowledge scores there was significant association was found with education of parents and previous knowledge.

Conclusion

The present study was undertaken to gauge the effectiveness of planned teaching programme on reproductive health care. The subsequent conclusion was supported the findings. During the researcher's field experience, it's been observed that the majority of the adolescent girls were unaware about anatomy and physiology of genital system, menstrual hygiene, abnormalities of cycle, STDs, tract infections, Nutritional measures permanently menstrual health. Hence planned teaching programme was effective strategy to reinforce within the knowledge.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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